

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for NURR1 (UniProt ID: P43354) for use in western blot

Riham Ayoubi¹, Sara González Bolívar¹, and Carl Laflamme^{1*}, NeuroSGC/YCharOS/EDDU collaborative group and ABIF consortium

¹ Department of Neurology and Neurosurgery, Structural Genomics Consortium, The Montreal Neurological Institute, McGill University, Montreal, Quebec, Canada

* Corresponding author: carl.laflamme@mcgill.ca

Abstract

The nuclear receptor related 1 (NURR1) is encoded by the nuclear receptor subfamily 4 group A member 2 (*NR4A2*) gene. The protein is a transcription factor essential for the differentiation of dopaminergic neurons and mutations in the corresponding gene are associated with Parkinson's disease. Here we have characterized nine NURR1 commercial antibodies for western blot using a standardized experimental protocol based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. These studies are part of a larger, collaborative initiative seeking to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercially available antibodies for human proteins and publishing the results openly as a resource for the scientific community. While use of antibodies and protocols vary between laboratories, we encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibodies for their specific needs.

Keywords:

UniProt ID: P43354, *NR4A2*, NURR1, Nuclear receptor subfamily 4 group A member 2, nuclear receptor related 1, Orphan nuclear receptor NURR1, antibody characterization, antibody validation, western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence

Introduction

NURR1 (*NR4A2*) is a member of the *NR4A* subfamily of transcription factors which also includes NUR77 (*NR4A1*) and NOR1 (*NR4A3*) (1). The NURR1 function is crucial for the formation of dopamine neurons in the midbrain (2) and mutations in the *NR4A2* gene are linked to Parkinson's disease (3).

This research is part of a broader collaborative initiative in which academics, funders and commercial antibody manufacturers are working together to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercial antibodies for human proteins using standardized protocols, and openly sharing the data (4-6). Here we evaluated the performance of nine commercial antibodies for NURR1 for use in western blot, enabling biochemical and cellular assessment of NURR1 properties and function. The platform for antibody characterization used to carry out this study was endorsed by a committee of industry and academic representatives. It consists of identifying human cell lines with adequate target protein expression and the development/contribution of equivalent knockout (KO) cell lines, followed by antibody characterization procedures using most commercially available antibodies against the corresponding protein. The standardized consensus antibody characterization protocols are openly available on Protocol Exchange, a preprint server (DOI:[10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1](https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1)) (7).

The authors do not engage in result analysis or offer explicit antibody recommendations. Our primary aim is to deliver top-tier data to the scientific community, grounded in Open Science principles. This empowers experts to interpret the characterization data independently, enabling them to make informed choices regarding the most suitable antibodies for their specific experimental needs. Guidelines on how to interpret antibody characterization data found in this study are featured on the YCharOS gateway (8).

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from wild type (WT) and KO cells (9, 10). The first step was to identify a cell line(s) that expresses sufficient levels of a given protein to generate a measurable signal using antibodies. To this end, we examined the DepMap (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655) transcriptomics database to identify all cell lines that express the target at levels greater than $2.5 \log_2$ (transcripts per million "TPM" + 1), which we have found to be a suitable cut-off (4). HeLa expresses the NURR1 transcript at 3.2 TPM on DepMap, which is above the average range of cancer cells analyzed. A *NR4A2* KO HeLa clonal cell line was generated (Table 1).

While RNA levels for NURR1 are detectable in a subset of cell lines, proteomic analyses from DepMap, as well as our western blot data (Figure 1A, first lane), indicate that NURR1 protein is barely detectable under basal culture conditions. Previous studies have shown that treatment with the PKC activator phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate (PMA) in serum-starved cells increases NURR1 mRNA levels (11). Consistently, we observed that these conditions in HeLa cells induced an increase in NURR1 protein levels, with detectable expression peaking at 2 hours post-treatment, as demonstrated by western blot analysis (Figure 1A).

To screen NURR1-specific antibodies, we used serum starvation followed by a 2-hour PMA treatment in both HeLa WT and (KO) cell lines. Lysates were run on SDS-PAGE, transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes, and then probed with all NURR1 antibodies in parallel. Among the antibodies tested, AF2156 specifically detected NURR1 protein, though a faint band was also observed in the KO cell line, suggesting residual NURR1 expression in the KO line (Figure 1B).

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. Firstly, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all commercially available NURR1 antibodies. YCharOS partners provide approximately 80% of all renewable antibodies, but some top-cited polyclonal antibodies may not be available through these partners.

Secondly, the YCharOS effort employs a non-biased approach that is agnostic to the protein for which antibodies have been characterized. The aim is to provide objective data on antibody performance without preconceived notions about how antibodies should perform or the molecular weight that should be observed in western blot. As the authors are not experts in NURR1 only a brief overview of the protein's function and its relevance in disease is provided. NURR1 experts are invited to analyze and interpret observed banding patterns in western blots and subcellular localization in immunofluorescence.

Thirdly, YCharOS experiments are not performed in replicates primarily due to the use of multiple antibodies targeting various epitopes. Once a specific antibody is identified, it validates the protein expression of the intended target in the selected cell line, confirms the lack of protein expression in the KO cell line and supports conclusions regarding the specificity of the other antibodies. All experiments are performed using master mixes, and meticulous attention is paid to sample preparation and experimental execution. In IF, the use of two different concentrations serves to evaluate antibody specificity and can aid in assessing assay reliability. In instances where antibodies yield no signal, a repeat experiment is conducted following titration. Additionally, our independent data is performed subsequently to the antibody manufacturers internal validation process, therefore making our characterization process a repeat.

Lastly, as comprehensive and standardized procedures are respected, any conclusions remain confined to the experimental conditions and cell line used for this study. The use of a single cell type for evaluating antibody performance poses as a limitation, as factors such as target protein abundance significantly impact results (7). Additionally, the use of cancer cell lines containing gene mutations poses a potential challenge, as these mutations may be within the epitope coding sequence or other regions of the gene responsible for the intended target. Such alterations can impact the binding affinity of antibodies. This represents an inherent limitation of any approach that employs cancer cell lines.

Method

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are openly available on Protocol Exchange, a preprint server (DOI: [10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1](https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1)) (7). Brief descriptions of the experimental setup used to carry out this study can be found below.

Cell lines and antibodies

Cell lines used and primary antibodies tested in this study are listed in Table 1 and 2, respectively. To ensure that the cell lines and antibodies are cited properly and can be easily identified, we have included their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers, or RRID (11, 12).

To induce NURR1 protein expression, HeLa cells were rinse three times in PBS 1x and incubated in serum-free medium for ~18 hrs. The next day, 200 ng/ml PMA (Abcam, cat. number ab120297) were added for various time points, indicated in Figure 1.

HeLa KO clone corresponding to the *NR4A2* gene was generated in the lab. Three guide RNAs were used to introduce a 76 bp deletion in exon 3 of the *NR4A2* gene (sequence guide 1: TAGTAAACCGACCCGGAGTG, sequence guide 2: ATCCCGGGTCGTCCACATG, seurence guide 3: CTGCTCGATCATGTGCGTAG).

Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse antibodies are from Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 65-6120 and 62-6520. Peroxidase-conjugated donkey anti-goat is from Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A15999. Alexa-555-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse secondary antibodies are from Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A-21429 and A-21424. Alexa-555-conjugated donkey anti-goat secondary antibodies is from Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number. A-21432.

Antibody screening by western blot

HeLa WT and *NR4A2* KO cells untreated or treated with PMA were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at ~110,000 x g for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder (GeneDireX, cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number WXP42012BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1610772), loaded in Laemmli loading sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number AAJ61337AD) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining

(Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Cell Signalling Technology, cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/ml in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 32106) or Clarity Western ECL Substrate (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1705061) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A44240).

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Competing interests

For this project, the laboratory of Peter McPherson developed partnerships with high-quality antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to the McPherson laboratory at no cost. These partners include: - Abcam-ABCD antibodies- ABclonal- Aviva Systems Biology -Bio Techne -Cell Signalling Technology -Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank - GeneTex – Horizon Discovery – Proteintech – Synaptic Systems –Thermo Fisher Scientific.

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Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Abcam	ab255928	CVCL_0030	HeLa	WT
Custom	-	-	HeLa	<i>NR4A2</i> KO

Table 2: Summary of the NURR1 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µL)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab54366*	1027118-6	AB_881748	monoclonal	447C2a	mouse	0.05	Wb
ABclonal	A22011	5500018095	AB_3083446	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.87	Wb
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP32730	QC77141-220420	AB_1042497	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP38754	QC8439-091126	AB_2047290	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Bio-Techne	AF2156	UUW062203	AB_2153894	polyclonal	-	goat	0.25	Wb, IF
FabGennix	NURR1-101AP	2244.PLD.IG	n/a	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.75	Wb, IP
Proteintech	10975-2-AP	113131	AB_2153760	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.7	Wb, IF
Proteintech	66878-1-Ig*	10007973	AB_2882211	monoclonal	1H5B4	mouse	1.00	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA5-13416	YJ4091622	AB_2153896	polyclonal	-	rabbit	2	Wb, IF

Wb=western blot; IF= immunofluorescence; IP=immunoprecipitation, *= monoclonal antibody, n/a=not available

Table 3: Illustrations to assess antibody performance in western blot.

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Figure 1: NURR1 antibody screening by western blot

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: NURR1 antibody screening by western blot.

A) Lysates of HeLa WT cells, under the corresponding conditions, were processed for western blot with the NURR1 antibody AF2156 used at 1/500 (0.5 µg/mL).

B) Lysates of HeLa (WT and *NR4A2* KO) under the corresponding conditions were prepared, and 60 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated NURR1 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KO lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilution used: ab54366* at 1/500, A22011 at 1/500, ARP32730 at 1/500 (1 µg/mL), ARP38754 at 1/500 (1 µg/mL), AF2156 at 1/500 (0.5 µg/mL), NURR1-101AP at 1/500, 10975-2-AP at 1/1000, 66878-1-Ig* at 1/500, PA5-13416 at 1/500. Antibodies AF2156, 66878-1-Ig* and PA5-13416 were titrated as the signal was too weak when following the supplier's recommendations. Predicted band size: 66.5 kDa *= monoclonal antibody.